
Research

Integration of enterprise social media into corporate South Africa: An investigation into data protection

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Abstract: The growing of new technologies and the increased adoption of social media by firms and individuals have increasingly become a common feature in the corporate world. Some firms have used this as an advantage and have in turn used this as part of the promotional tool to make their products and services known, grow their businesses, win customers over and at the same time, make profits. Faced with growing business competition, some companies have now resorted to the use of social media, as an important tool of trade when it comes to improving business operations as well as in gaining and maintaining market share. If not handled well, however, social media can turn in to a nightmare, as it may result in the circulation of viral messages which may in turn tarnish the image of the company. This calls for the need for government to ensure that data protection measures are in place in order to ensure that toxic information does not go out in to the public domain. Through an archival method of data protection, this article investigates data protection in South Africa's social media enterprise. The article reveals that, social media does play an important role in improving the operations of most companies, and hence, the need for stern data protection measures to control the kind of information that goes to the public.

Keywords: Corporate, Enterprise Social Media, Data Protection, South Africa, Customers

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Introduction

The emergence of ESM sites like Facebook, Twitter, MySpace, instagram, whatsapp, and Wechat has created an opportunity for business organisations to communicate internally and also to the outside world (Leonardi, Huysman and Steinfield, 2013). This has made Enterprise Social Media a powerful platform in which organisations communicate with their customers (Swart, Plessis and Greef, 2021). It has therefore been regarded as an overcomer of time and geographical constraints (Dunbar, 2016). Enterprise Social Media gives people the chance to connect to each other, discuss issues as well as make inquiries about a company's products services (Verma & Verma, 2017; Tala, Nathelia and Catherine, 2018). Faced with rapid change in technologies, people and organisations have been able to utilise Social media platforms such as, whatsapp, facebook and twitter to communicate in the easier and faster manner

(Ghanem & Hamid, 2020). It has there become possible for firms and customers to quickly spread information through Social Media networks. If not used correctly however, the use of social media can do an organisation more harm than good. This is because bad publicity can be fuelled and spread fast through Social media networks in such a way that a company may end up losing more business than expected. It however becomes important for organisation to control information that may go out to the public. The government must also have laws and policies that guide the nature of information that goes out to the public as well. The article delves into understanding the role that social media have played in smoothening the operations of corporate South Africa, and at the same time, investigates on issues revolving around issues of data protection in relation to social media. The article seeks to address the following research objectives:

1. To access the role of enterprise social media in improving business operations of South African corporates.
2. To evaluate the level or extent of data protection by the South African government when dealing with social media.

Conceptual Framework

The article acknowledges that enterprise media forms an important part in gaining and retaining customers as well as in increasing sales revenues for businesses in the long run (Lockett, 2018; Saridakis, Lai, Mohammed and Hansen, 2018). The article acknowledges the RACE Framework as an important part of the research study. Emanating from the REAN Framework which meant reach-engage—activate-nurture, RACE is a framework that stands for reach-act-convert and engage (Chaffey & Ellis-Chadwick, 2016) It helps managers to improve the organisation’s commercial value through digital marketing.

The Race Framework (adapted from Smart Insights and Oxford College of Marketing)

The model aims to build awareness through web platforms as well as engage and communicate with customers online. It aims to build client relationships throughout the passage of time in order to achieve retention goals.

4.1.1 Reach

In order to reach customers, companies may utilise offline platforms which may be through advertising on billboards, then build more customers by referring to the company website and social media platforms (Chaffey & Smith, 2017). In measuring success, key performance indicators which include the rate at which social media platforms such as Facebook are visited by new people, can be used to measure progress. In this regard, a company may erect bill boards in the city centre to alert people of what the company offers. Written on these billboards, will be the company's website and various links to its social media platforms such as Facebook, Twitter and WhatsApp, to mention but a few. This will in turn lure more people to visit the company's social media pages to get more information about the company, and possible promotions which may be on offer. Similarly, the company may also advertise on radio and television and link more people to the company's social media pages by revealing the links on these platforms.

4.1.2 Act

This stage is highly interactive (Chaffey & Ellis-Chadwick, 2019). Here, the audience is engaged with the company on the company's website. Companies make use of other online platforms such as Facebook, WhatsApp and Instagram to encourage interaction with customers. Companies can also make use of blogs and emails and in measuring a company's success, page visits should be high and people must be engaged in various conversations and product promotions. At this stage, the audience is led on a path to purchasing the company's products through online icons such as "Viewed product", "Added to Basket", "Registered as member" or through signing up for an e-newsletter (Chaffey, 2020). This way, the audience is always constantly updated about the company's products and promotions.

4.1.3 Convert

This stage involves conversion to sale either through online or offline channels (Chaffey, 2020). This stage requires companies to take that important step which converts them into paying customers either online or through offline channels. The success for firms will then be measured by the number of sales, revenues collected as well as the profit margins made by the company. In this case, social media platforms will have to be used to convince customers to also buy the products being marketed. On its Facebook page, a company can upload videos to further explain what the company offers and these will be meant to win customers over. It then becomes competitive for the company to market its business in a unique way, which will be more better than its competitors.

4.1.4 Engage

This aims to engage and communicate with customers on a long term basis, and this can be achieved through development of a long term relationship with first-time buyers and this helps in building customer loyalty (Chaffey, 2020). Customer loyalty makes customers trust more in the products being offered by the particular company (Leninkumar, 2017), and this may make it very unlikely for a customer to change where it usually buy its products or subcontracts its services. Success can be measured through repeat purchases by customers as well as their ability to share content and testimonies through social media platforms. By so doing, the needs and expectations of customers are well taken care of, and as customer confidence builds, the customer may become even more loyal and continue buying the company's products in future.

Theoretical Underpinnings

This article adopts the social media privacy model. Trepte (2021) defines privacy as the selective control that guides information sharing. Social media privacy is mainly based on interpersonal processes of mutual communication (Petronio, 2002). Trepte (2021) emphasises that the social media privacy model is based on the following propositions:

Proposition 1: Privacy is interdependently valued and perceived

Social media platforms have been considered as platforms that aim to ensure connectedness, sociality and interconnectedness and are therefore regarded as social centred (Ellison & boyd, 2013). It is also argued that, social media privacy can be achieved by exerting control, which is alternatively perceived to be at the centre of the individual person and can be considered as ego-centred (Papacharissi, 2010; Sarikakis & Winter, 2017; Trepte, 2021).

Proposition 2: Privacy cannot only be satisfactorily achieved by exercising control in social media

In this case, it is advocated that, not only control is necessary to ensure privacy when it comes to social media platforms. The need to constantly engage in interpersonal communication between the individual and the company or institution becomes necessary in order to ensure privacy in social media (Trepte, 2021).

Proposition 3: Interpersonal communication helps in ensuring that social media privacy is put in action

It is noted that, not all social media actions are accompanied by communication. In many instances, people would rely on past experiences and in this case, trust becomes an important factor in ensuring privacy. Saeri (2014), stresses that trust is considered a crucial factor of influence when it comes to decisions concerning self-disclosure. A study conducted showed that, people substituted trust for control (Teutsch, Masur, and Trepte, 2018), whilst Eichenhofer (2019) suggests that the trust paradigm should point towards a more recent or current perspective on privacy regulation through trust as compared to privacy regulation via self-determination or control. In this case of private regulation, both social and legislative norms come into play (Gusy, 2018; Spottswood & Hancock, 2017). Social norms can be defined as social pressure to engage in certain kinds of behaviours and are established on the basis of what others approve as well as what they actually do (Saeri et al., 2014). Although legislative norms are regulated by law and coined by jurisprudence, they also share with social norms in the sense that, they also prescribe certain behaviour (Trepte, 2021). Other scholars have stressed that, trust and norms are key factors in obtaining privacy and to establish trust and norms, communication becomes very essential (Marwick & boyd, 2014; Quinn, 2014).

Proposition 4 Norms and trust act as privacy mechanisms

In this instance, users do not only rely on control but also aim to communicate about privacy issues as a way to establish norms and trust and in other instances regain control (Trepte, 2021). It is further argued that, the type of mechanism that can be used by a company to ensure privacy is mainly influenced by the type of content that is being shared as well as the social media affordances (Trepte, 2021). The model however, has its own challenges and these shall now be discussed at this juncture.

Challenges of the Social Media Privacy Model

This article acknowledges the many benefits attached to social media such as freedom of speech, its ability not to recognize geographical boundaries, and its ability to allow people to practice freedom of speech (Trepte, 2021). It has often been argued that, privacy is historically linked to freedom and that, freedom is the origin in genealogy of privacy and in legislation (Gusy, 2018). Studies have however, acknowledged that, in the concept of privacy as a communicative process, not all members have an equal chance of being heard as motivated by digital and literacy gaps which have been shown to heavily influence the communicative process of people in these communicative processes (Helsper, 2017). There is also lack or limited control over personal information in social media, and it is this lack of control that is usually stressful and demanding (Trepte, 2021). Through the use of social media, electronic devices such as video phones and camera have the capability of capturing any crisis that unfolds and this information can be misinterpreted by journalists (Ramluckan et al, 2016). Social media have been used by businesses as an effective way

to market the company’s name, its services, as well as its products, and have in turn have a positive impact on the growth of many businesses. This article now looks at Social media sites and the corporate world.

Social Media sites and the Corporate world

The world is now comprised of digital natives (Tuten, 2020), a phase which means someone born in the era of digital technology .A research from 31 countries showed that, of the 31 surveyed countries, 91% of them used smart phones in the first hour of waking up, usually before they go out of bed (Lee & Calugar-Pop, 2016). This shows the addictive nature of people on their phones and the ability of them to easily access information from their mobile phones as soon as in the early hours of the morning. This shows the ability of people to easily access information through their smartphones, which acts as an advantage for businesses when it comes to making information available to the public. Social media tools can also capture and preserve situations that may result from crisis situations and this have helped businesses in terms of managing information in crisis preparedness, impact and responses to various crises (Ramluckan, Subban and McArthur, 2016). Figure 1 represents the different usage rate of various social media sites by people.

Figure 1: Facts about Social Media Sites (Doherty in Tuten, 2020)

It can be noted that Facebook has the largest number of users amounting to 2.3 billion people, followed by Instagram which have around 1 billion users, Linked Inn which is highly professional has 706 million users, whilst Twitter, Snapchat and Pinterest have 306 million, 210 million and 291 million users respectively. It can be shown that, Facebook is the most dominant site.

Facebook and Corporates

Social media sites such as Facebook have managed to bridge the gap between corporates and the public in a much faster way. This is because, information have managed to reach the public in a faster and more convenient way. This have also been evidenced by the use of cell phones (which are much cheaper) by people to access social media sites. Ruehl & Ingenhoff (2016) argue that corporates have increasingly adopted the use of social media networks from a

communication and management perspective, as they have increasingly appreciated the role played by these platforms such as Facebook to offer convenient communication when it comes to communicating with stakeholders directly on these online communication sites.

Other studies have however, raised a lot of concerns about Facebook privacy issues and negatives associated with the use of these Facebook sites. A study by Van der Schyff, Flowerday and Furnell (2020) reveals that, females are particularly vulnerable to privacy risks due to their continued use of Facebook, whilst Van der Schyff, Krauss and Kroeze, (2018), further argue that, these social media platforms such as Facebook, does come with hidden agendas aimed at constantly monitoring and gathering information about users with the major intension to capitalise. This in turn reveals the need for users to be protected as it shows a 'lack' in privacy issues.

WhatsApp and Corporates

WhatsApp has also emerged as an important marketing tool for most business (Balarade, 2020). This has been because of its ability for people to communicate in real time with business representatives about certain issues of concern. Through WhatsApp, groups can be created and a larger audience can be reached. Also, people can get to say out their views and complaints in a quicker manner.

A study carried out in Kano metropolis, revealed that WhatsApp and Instagram have successfully been used by businesses as effective advertising tools (Balarade, 2020). Another study carried out on small business start-ups in Nigeria's Abuja Municipal Area Council revealed that, the use of WhatsApp does have a positive impact on business growth in Nigeria and that it also had potential to improve ease of doing business (Negedu & Isik, 2020). This shows the importance of the use of WhatsApp by businesses as it has been seen to positively contribute to business growth in some firms.

This shows that a lot of people do use social media platforms for various reasons and through the use of these platforms, businesses can reach a wider audience in the shortest possible time. This shows the dominant use of social media platforms by people and an advantage for businesses when it comes to adoption of these platforms for marketing of businesses and their products as well as services offered.

Instagram

Instagram is defined as a social networking application that enables user interaction through the sharing of videos and photos from their phones or computers (Moreau, 2018). Soffar (2018) argues that, Instagram improves communication even at the global level. This means that people from different continents can interact and share ideas. Having an Instagram account allows people even those out of the country to be aware of the company services and this can improve on business as they can also get contracts from outside the country, thus gaining foreign currency. Clients can be interacted with at global level and in so doing, companies can in turn tune products to suit the international standard as there will be the sharing of ideas. This would in turn mean, businesses' quality standards may be improved. Oji, Iwu and Tenge (2017) acknowledge that some businesses use social media platforms more than others and other well-known social media sites includes YouTube, LinkedIn and Snapchat.

Social Media as a hindrance to Business Growth

It is however important to note that, in some instances, social media can act as a hindrance to business growth, as it can ruin a company's reputation (Ji, Li, North & Liu, 2017). This becomes a reality in cases whereby customers talk bad about the company services and its products. This in turn instils the lack of zeal in new customers to try the company's products and services. In cases of complaints, a company must be very careful and tactful in addressing customer queries, as well as when it comes to improving company's services and their product portfolio, as a way to remain ahead of competitors.

Customers can complain about any offensive act by the company's staff on the company's Facebook page, or about anything that may relate to the product of interest. Videos of customers complaining and demonstrating how the product of the company have ill-performed can be posted on the company's social media pages such as Facebook, and this may caught the attention of a larger audience and this can quickly spread through viral marketing. Elison (2017) argues that many people spend an average 30 minutes per day on Facebook. This shows how powerful the platform is as people get as many updates as possible in the minimum possible time. World statistics show that, 39.3% of Africans have access to the internet (Internet World Stats, 2021). This shows a significant uptake of the platform by Africans and businesses can take advantage of this in order to reach as many customers as possible when it comes to making their products and services known. This would be done with the intension to gain as much market share as possible, and to make as much profits as possible. The article now looks at incorporation of social media into corporate South Africa.

Corporate South Africa and Social Media

Social media have been regarded as the heart of human communication as it bears many advantages such as practicing freedom of speech as well as the ability to reach out to many people in critical living conditions, including providing them with support (Trepte, 2021). The use of social media in marketing has been regarded as an important tool by many businesses as it has been associated with numerous advantages. Dwivedi, Ismagilova, Rana, and Raman (2021) argue that, social media does play an important role in the digital transformation of businesses. A quantitative study carried out on 234 tourism Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) managers in Free State, South Africa showed that in the tourism sector social media marketing was positively related to competitiveness of tourism SMEs (Rambe, 2017).

It is however argued that, regardless of claims that more people use social media, there have been reports from both scholarly and mainstream media that, over half of the world's population remains offline (Oji et al., 2017). Various claims to the lack in social media uptake have pointed to high cost of devices, lack of infrastructure and inability of smaller companies to effectively adopt and embrace new technologies, and hence, the need for smaller companies to embrace new technologies in order for them to have creative ways to reach out to customers and potential customers. (Oji et al., 2017).

A study carried out on small restaurants in Cape Metropole revealed that access to internet was one of the prominent factors that hindered the adoption of the internet by restaurants that were surveyed, the lack of understanding of the role of social media, lack of interest and marketing strategies (Oji et al., 2017). Kimani (2014) in Oji et al 2017 argued that, social media platforms such as Twitter, WhatsApp and Facebook have been used as intermediaries for customer relations management. Swart, du Plessis and Greeff (2021) acknowledges the positive role played by social media in South Africa's non-profit organisation and through a study, it was concluded that, corporates should practice an integrated social media communication approach as an alternative way of practicing content marketing in the non-profit sector. The advent of EMS has made it possible for banks and other financial institutions to communicate to their board members at a fast and easy way which could not have been possible before (Yeboah, 2022)

Data Protection and Corporates in South Africa

As cyber technologies become more advanced, users become exposed to more privacy threats (Nyoni and Velepini, 2015). The issue of data protection have been one that have been associated with statutes, treaties, regulations, information campaigns and agencies, which must be coordinated with complex legislation and policies on cyber security (Sutherland, 2021).

It has been postulated that regulatory frameworks and legal instruments are currently lacking a strong cyber presence for the protection of users and argues that laws are more of reactive to cyber-crimes in South Africa (Nyoni and Velempini, 2015; Sutherland, 2021).

It has been assumed that although the South African government have good policies, it struggles to keep up with the pace of the increased changes in social advancements, especially in cases of newly introduced social media networks and the behavior that follows it, especially during work hours and outside the work environments (Electronic Communication Act, 2005 In Mkomazi, 2020). Ramluckan, Subban and McArthur (2016) acknowledges that, online media platforms have the greatest impact due to its accessibility and the way people collect and spread or disseminate information is rapidly expanding. Ramluckan et al (2016) also suggest that the internet spreads information fast and offers real time access to multimedia via search engines, blogs, email, podcasts as well as through other sites such as Youtube and Flickr. Ramluckan et al (2016) acknowledges the existence of various legislative tools for the control of social media in South Africa and these include:-

- The Constitution of South Africa Act 108 of 1996
- The Electronic Communications and Transactions Act No. 25 of 2002
- Protection and Personal Information Act 4 of 2013 and RICA and the
- The Regulation of Interception of Communication and Provision of Communication Related Information Act

The Constitution of South Africa Act 108 (1996)

Section 1 of the Constitution of South Africa Act together with the King III were designed to ensure accountability, responsiveness and openness by democratic government and some corporative crises (Ramluckan et al., 2016). In this regard, organisations had to be accountable for their own actions especially considering the fact that the general public remained their main clientele and surrounding communities, with social media being one of the most relevant tool to communicate with the relevant stakeholders (Ramluckan et al., 2016).

Section 14 reinforces the need to ensure privacy (Cawthra, 2020). This right is in turn infringed by social media to a certain extent especially when it comes to public figures (Ramluckan et al., 2016). This is mainly because social media promotes freedom of expression, and in some cases, where a matter may revolve around specific people with crises, privacy of these persons must be upheld.

Section 16 of the constitution protects the right to freedom of expression but limits hate speech (Ramluckan et al., 2016). This may in turn create some level of contradiction between section 14 and 16.

The Electronic Communications and Transactions Act 25 of 2002

The Electronic Communications and Transactions (ECT) Act 25 of 2002 was designed as a guide towards the responsible use of social media and was designed to maximise on benefits provided by the internet such as promoting the universal access of internet in disadvantaged areas as well as ensuring that the needs of communities are taken into consideration (Ramluckan et al., 2016). It also enables the identification, protection and management of critical databases and critical data. It is however argued that The Electronics Communications and Transaction Act (ECTA), Act No. 25 of 2002 was established in an era where more emphasis was placed on voice calls and when internet usage was relatively low in South Africa (Government Gazette, 2021.)

The Protection and Personal Information Act (POPIA) 4 of 2013

The South African government drafted the POPI bill in 2009 and this was published in the Government Gazette in November 2013 with the main aim to ensure that the privacy of South Africans would be protected (Ramluckan et al., 2016). POPI applies to all the people of South Africa processing information and this includes companies, employees and individuals (Cawthra, 2020). The Act was created to:-

- Establish a channel in which information would be collected
- Ensure the establishments of an Information Regulatory Body that would regulate how information would be collected
- Regulate how information flows across the South African borders as well as
- Provide rights to South Africans that may receive unsolicited information

(Ramluckan et al, 2016; Government Gazzete, 2021)

This Act would therefore control the release of information by individuals, employees and companies and this would in turn help to control the type of information that would be received by the general public. This would in turn regulate the nature of information released to the general public.

Regulation of Interception of Communication and Provision of Communication Related Information Act, 2002 (RICA).

The Regulation of Interception of Communication and Provision of Communication Related Information Act was designed as a way to monitor the interception of communications and this included the monitoring of radio frequencies and radio signals as well as the provision of communication related information relating to the records of telecommunication service providers ((Ramluckan et al., 2016). The act also provides for the formation of interception centres and forbids the assembling, manufacturing, possessing, selling, purchasing or the advertising of interception equipment without a certificate of exemption issues by the minister ((Ramluckan et al., 2016).

Government Gazette, 2021

<p>South African Cybersecurity Framework, 2012</p>	<p>Provides for a secure, dependable, reliable and trustworthy cyber environment that facilitates the protection of critical information infrastructure whilst strengthening shared human values and the understanding of cybersecurity in support of national security imperatives and the economy.</p>
<p>National Integrated ICT Policy White Paper, 2016</p>	<p>Provides for an open data policy framework with the following policy objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Set out the principles that will inform the development of an open data action plan to allow everyone to access, use and re-use non-personal and unclassified public information and data. • Make non-personal and unclassified government-held data more widely available and usable, taking into account the South African legal context. • Promote informed, active citizenship by providing the framework to facilitate access to public data. • Promote innovation and economic growth by facilitating greater access to data which will enable entrepreneurs to better understand their communities and markets. • Promote efficiency and cost-effectiveness in the public sector by making it easier and less costly for government entities to access and re-use their own data and that of other public agencies. • Promote evidence-based policy making across government. The policy further emphasises commitment to ensure that key non-personal public information and data are freely available to everyone to use, re-use and republish as they wish, subject only to restrictions to protect privacy, confidentiality and security in line with the Constitution.

Methodology

The study adopted the archival method to data collection and the primary data collection from companies through online questionnaires. In the archival method to data collection, existing secondary scholarly sources were reviewed and these were mostly found on google scholar. These gave the idea of the adoption of social media sites by South African companies and also explored on privacy and data protection issues.

In the primary collection of data were used and information was collected from companies through online questionnaires. Data will be analysed through the Statistical Package for Social Scientists (SPSS) and results were presented through graphs and tables.

Results

Fig 1 shows summary of view on Integration of Enterprise Social Media into Corporate South Africa that is determining whether it have benefits to a firm or not? It indicates that over 50 percent are benefiting from social media.

Fig 2

The survey also came up with age groups of individuals who are using social media platforms. The results on the graph below shows that youthly age group are the most people using social media and above 45 are not active on social platforms. It is assumed that youth and young adult are active in using social media platforms because they are highly involved at work places in organization. Also youth and adults have a high connection of friends which is easier to spread information among youth where as adults' connection of friends tend to have a more diverse age distribution.

Fig 3

The graphs further explain the relationship between age groups and social media platform that the organization uses to reach out. Results show that, Facebook has recorded the highest and the most used across all age groups, this might imply that Facebook is of more benefit when advertising a new product or selling products. It clearly shows that LinkedIn, a professional platform is used by people of ages 23 up to 54. The reason is these are the working class groups and job seekers and one might conclude that if business is professional and targeting young youths and ages up to 54, LinkedIn as a social platform is most recommended.

Fig 4

Nature of bussiness of the company is also another key to be considered. The results shows that companies that specializes in Telecommunication and Agricultures has the highest effect where as education and freight and logistics has the lowest effect.

The following two tables shows the responses on nature of business and the impact of enterprise social media in marketing and in improving the operations of corporates in South Africa. At 5% level of significance, there is no relationship between nature of business and the impact of enterprise social media in marketing and in improving the operations of corporates in South Africa.

		Thirty_one					Total
		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	
Nature_of_Business	Manufacturing	1	5	1	3	3	13
	Telecomms	1	5	6	4	1	17
	Mining	3	4	4	3	1	15
	Agriculture	3	3	5	1	4	16
	FMCG	4	0	2	5	0	11
	Banking	1	3	3	2	1	10
	Retail	3	1	0	3	1	8
	Tourism and Hospitality	1	3	0	0	2	6
	Education	0	2	1	0	0	3
Total	17	26	22	21	13	99	

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	37.206 ^a	32	.242
Likelihood Ratio	45.297	32	.060
Linear-by-Linear Association	.647	1	.421
N of Valid Cases	99		

Fig 5

Educational levels as shown in fig 5 reflects that ESM also contributes to business growth as it shows that Matric up to grade has the highest usage, however it might need to be considered as a less busy level than that of a post-graduate levels where one is writing articles or is a business owner working on how to improve the business.

Table 1: Age and Education Level

		Age					Total
		18-24	23-34	35-44	45-54	55 and Above	
Education	Matric upto Grade	8	15	6	10	5	44
	National Certificate	9	4	5	3	0	21
	National Diploma	0	1	6	0	3	10
	Bacahelors Degree	3	5	2	0	2	12
	Masters Degree	4	4	0	0	0	8
	Postgrad Certificate	0	1	0	0	1	2
	Postgrad diploma	1	0	0	0	0	1
	Postgrad degree	0	0	1	0	0	1
Total		25	30	20	13	11	99

Table 2 Chi square tests between age and education level

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	47.376 ^a	28	.012
Likelihood Ratio	52.926	28	.003
Linear-by-Linear Association	1.437	1	.231
N of Valid Cases	99		

a. 34 cells (85.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .11.

The data test at null hypothesis whether education and age are independent of each other. The chi-square value of 47.376 at p value 0.012 is significant which explains that education and age are associated with each other when analysing the impact of social media in an organization.

Table 3: Chi-square test between Gender and Education

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	16.699 ^a	7	.019
Likelihood Ratio	19.300	7	.007
Linear-by-Linear Association	.111	1	.739
N of Valid Cases	99		

The chi-square results show that at 99% level of significance gender and education has the relationship on impact of social media with a chi-square value of 16.999 at p-value 0.019.

Correlations and Pearson Correlation

Pearson correlation is a measure of linear correlation between two sets of data. It is the ratio between the covariance of two variables and the product of their standard deviations. It is essentially a normalized measurement of the covariance, such that the result always has a value between -1 and 1. As with covariance itself, the measure can only reflect a linear correlation of variables, and ignores many other types of relationships or correlations. From the following table, there is a negative relationship between gender and age as well as gender and educational level which have a correlation values of -0.94 and -0.34 respectively however the relationship between gender and social media platform and nature of business has a positive relationship.

Table: Pearson correlation relationship

		Gender	Education	Social_Media_Platform	Age	Nature_of_Business
Gender	Pearson Correlation	1	-.034	.021	-.094	.058
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.740	.835	.355	.571
	N	99	99	99	99	99
Education	Pearson Correlation	-.034	1	-.126	-.121	-.076
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.740		.213	.233	.455
	N	99	99	99	99	99
Social_Media_Platform	Pearson Correlation	.021	-.126	1	-.005	-.057
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.835	.213		.960	.574
	N	99	99	99	99	99
Age	Pearson Correlation	-.094	-.121	-.005	1	.013
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.355	.233	.960		.898
	N	99	99	99	99	99
Nature_of_Business	Pearson Correlation	.058	-.076	-.057	.013	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.571	.455	.574	.898	
	N	99	99	99	99	99

Comparing educational level and how does Interpersonal communication helps in enduring that social media privacy is put in action. The table shows a summary of responses in each educational level.

		Four					Total
		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	
Education	Matric upto Grade	4	20	12	7	1	44
	National Certificate	3	6	4	5	3	21
	National Diploma	0	2	5	0	3	10
	Bacahelors Degree	1	2	6	2	1	12
	Masters Degree	2	4	1	1	0	8
	Postgrad Certificate	0	0	1	0	1	2
	Postgrad diploma	0	0	0	1	0	1
	Postgrad degree	0	0	0	1	0	1
Total		10	34	29	17	9	99

Table: Chi-square test between educational level

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	37.737 ^a	28	.103
Likelihood Ratio	36.233	28	.137
Linear-by-Linear Association	2.319	1	.128
N of Valid Cases	99		

The results of a chi-square distribution at 5% level of significance shows that the relationship between education and Interpersonal communication in enduring that social media privacy is put in action is not significant.

Discussion

The aim of the research is to assess the role of enterprise social media in improving business operations of corporate South Africa and also to evaluate the level or extent of data protection by the South African government when dealing with Social media sites. The results show that age and education are intertwined. The youth are the most active users on the ESM platforms. Most ESM platforms have a tool where users can like and comment on post to express their views on products. Their comments and likes on posts are seen by their friends and followers on the platforms, this intends advertise the organisations indirectly. ESM consist of many platforms but the study shows that Facebook is the most frequently used social media; this means facebook has more benefits when it comes to marketing and advertising. Other social media site like LinkedIn is used mainly by job seekers and recruiters. Most business organisations use ESM as a way of messaging or advertising, this helps to sell the organisations to the outside world. On the educational level the study found out that from lower grades up to matric are the highest users of ESM with postgraduates being the lowest users. Highly educated people who are in high offices are busier and have less time to use ESM. Government offices and private companies all uses ESM in one way or the other, which means personal information and data of individuals and companies can be exposed if not protected.

Conclusions and Recommendations

The study is about ESM and its importance to corporate South Africa. Enterprise social media is very beneficial to business organisations in South Africa; this is so because of its profound advantages to organisations and their workers alike. ESM can be used to improve a good working relationship between managers and employees (Yeboah & Lewis, 2022). Aside from improving efficiency and productivity for organisations; it also ensures that employees and customers are happy. Employees are able to communicate at any time of the day by sharing messages through the use of ESM with their phones or computers. Businesses are able to advertise their products, set up virtual meetings with investors and customers and training of their employees through ESM, employees are able to work remotely from any part of the world through ESM (Yeboah, Yuan & Xuan, 2021). This put the data of organisations and businesses at risk because they are exposed to the outside world through ESM. The study is of the recommendation that organisations must buy their own network security protections and firewalls to protect their data. Organisations and businesses must educate their employees on how to use ESM effectively in other not to jeopardise their sensitive data. The government must play their part by strengthen and implementing the information technology laws of South Africa to prevent data breeches.

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